

COST, RETURNS AND PROFITABILITY OF SOYBEAN CULTIVATION IN HINGOLI DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA STATE

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Abstract

Present study was designed to measure input use, cost structure and return in soybean production of Hingoli district of Maharashtra, India. In present investigation the sample of 90 soybean farmers were selected from study area with a view to examine the input use, cost structure and returns in production and marketing of soybean growers in year 2020-21. The present study was undertaken in Hingoli district of Maharashtra. Cost-A was ₹. 52163.17 and Cost-B was ₹. 89325.76, for a total cost per hectare of ₹. 93179.64 for soybeans. Cost-A represented 55.98 per cent of the total cost, while Cost-B represented 95.86 per cent. The output-input ratio was 1.35, showing that the soybean production is really profitable. Significant factors included the surrounding area, hired human labour, seed, fertilizer, machine labour, and family labour.

Keywords: Soybean, Cost, Returns, Profitability

Introduction

In India, soybean (*Glycine max L.*) is known as the "golden bean" and is the most important crop farmed for dual purposes: oil seed and pulse crop. It is a key natural source of protein that contains a variety of amino acids that are necessary for optimum health. Glycine is derived from the Greek term 'Glykus,' which means 'sweet tuber.' Glycine is a wild genus that belongs to the leguminosae family and is native to China. The leguminosae family's phaseolae tribe is the most economically important. It is the world's most important oilseed crop. The Yellow River region of China is often regarded as the soybean origin.

Soybean may be cultivated successfully in a wide range of agroclimatic settings, from temperate to sub-tropical and tropical. Despite the fact that soybean is a legume crop, it is frequently employed as an oil seed crop. It cannot be used as a pulse crop because of its poor cookability due to the presence of a 'trypsin' inhibitor. Soybeans are high in protein and contain 18-20 per cent oil, as well as other vital amino acids and vitamins. Soybean oil is high in lecithin and vitamin A. Because of these features, soybean is commonly utilized in human diets and is referred to as "poor man's meat." It is known in China as the "Yellow Jewell," a great treasure of Chinese and vegetable meat. It is also known in America as the "Cinderella crop," "a king without a crown," and "a marvel bean."

Marathwada region constitutes Aurangabad, Jalna, Parbhani, Beed, Hingoli, Latur, Osmanabad and Nanded districts of Maharashtra. During the year 2021, Latur district ranked top in the Marathwada region in terms of area (4.42 lakh hectares) and output (7.74 lakh MT) with productivity (1750 kg/ha). In 2021, the area under soybean in Hingoli district was (2.35 lakh hectares) and production of (2.54 lakh MT) with productivity (1081), ranking six in area, production, and productivity in Maharashtra's Marathwada region. (Source: www. Krishi. Maharashtra. Gov. in)

Materials and Methods

For the 2020-21 study year, data on associated parts of the study were collected by a survey method from sample cultivars. The data was collected using a pre-tested interview. The survey approach was used to collect data on relevant factors such as input utilization, and cost of different inputs, yield obtained, soybean farming, and marketing from sample growers. Farmers were interviewed in person at their farms and residences, as well as in some cases in public venues in the village. The data was gathered according to a study-specific, pre-tested time table.

Results and Discussion**1. Physical inputs and outputs in soybean production.**

Physical inputs and outputs of soybean production calculated per hectare are shown in Table 1. On soybean farms, hired human labour was used 21.39 days, along with bullock labour 6.33 day. On the other hand, the use of bullock labour in soybean was less than the use of machine labour, at 6.33 days and 10.70 hours respectively. For

soybean, 66.78 kg of seeds were used, 19.07 quintals were utilized for manures. There were 18.04 kg of urea, 23.34 kg of 10:26:26, 31.11 kg of DAP, 148.1 kg of SSP, 16.27 kg of MOP and 51.39 kg of 10:32:16. For soybean, 0.73 lit of pesticides and 0.58 lit of fungicides was realized to be used. Use of family human labour was 17.15 days. It was also observed that main produce yield of soybean was 18.57 quintals and by produce yield was 2.86 quintals.

2. Per hectare cost of cultivation of soybean production.

The cost of growing soybean per hectare was determined and shown in Table 2. The outcome showed that the cost of cultivation per hectare was ₹.52163.17, of which Cost-A comprised 55.98 per cent, Cost-B was ₹.89325.76, which is 95.86 per cent, and Cost-C was ₹.93179.64, which is 100 per cent respectively. The amount spent on machine labour was ₹.11724.98, or 12.58 per cent. The major item of expenses is the rental value of the land, which is ₹.20908.18 or 22.44 per cent, hired human labour accounted to ₹.5321.66 or 5.71 per cent, seed ₹.7521.4 or 8.07 per cent, family human labour ₹.3853.88 or 4.14 per cent, interest on working capital ₹.2433.67 or 2.61 per cent, fertilizer ₹.4156.58 or 4.47 per cent, manure accounted, ₹.5720.9 or 6.14 per cent, bullock labour ₹.4034.4 or 4.33 per cent, interest on fixed capital ₹.16254.41 or 17.44 per cent, depreciation on farm assets ₹.9092.69 or 9.76 per cent, incidental charges ₹.325.45 or 0.35 per cent, plant protection ₹.1755.88 or 1.88 per cent and land revenue ₹. 75.56 or 0.08 per cent respectively. It was concluded that considerable amounts of bullock labour were replaced by machine labour.

Profitability in soybean production.

The profitability of producing soybean per hectare was determined and shown in table 3. The findings showed that the gross return per hectare in the soybean farm, was ₹.125902.47. It was evident that agricultural business income, family labour income, and net profit/ha were, ₹.73739.3, ₹.36576.71, and ₹.32722.83 respectively. The output-input ratio in soybean production was 1.35. Growing soybean was a successful business. The price of producing one quintal of soybean was ₹. 4737.86.

Conclusion

The present investigation was intended to depict the picture of the soybean growing enterprise in Hingoli districts. The per hectare soybean cultivation, it was observed that use of hired human labour, machine or tractor, plant protection chemical and chemical fertilizer are more utilized as increased in size of farms. It was also noticed that per hectare bullock labour decreased with increased in size of farms because of more utilized machine or tractor used. The total cost of soybeans, or cost C, per hectare was Rs. 93179.64, of which Rs. 52163.17 and Rs. 89325.76 were contributed by costs A and B, respectively. profit on costs A, B, and C were, respectively, Rs. 73739.3, Rs. 36576.71, and Rs. 32722.83. The output-input ratio was 1.35, which shows that growing soybeans is a very successful business.

Table 1: Per hectare physical input and output of Soybean farm (Unit/ha)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Unit	Average
	INPUT		
1.	Hired human labour	man days	
	Male		10.14
	Female		11.25
2.	Family human labour	man days	
	Male		8.77
	Female		8.38
3.	Bullock labour	pair days	6.33
4.	Machine labour	hours	10.70
5.	Seed	kg	66.78
6.	Manures	qt.	19.07
7.	Fertilizer		
	Urea	kg	18.04
	10:26:26	kg	23.34
	DAP	kg	31.11
	SSP	kg	148.1
	MOP	kg	16.27
	10:32:16	kg	51.39
8.	Plant Protection		
	Pesticides	lit	0.73
	Fungicides	lit	0.58
9.	OUTPUT		
	Main produce	qt.	18.57
	By produce	qt.	2.86

Table 2: Per hectare cost of cultivation of soybean crop (₹/ha)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Amount (₹)	Per cent
1.	Hired human labour	5321.66	5.71
2.	Machine labour	11724.98	12.58
3.	Bullock labour	4034.4	4.33
4.	Seed	7521.4	8.07
5.	Manure	5720.9	6.14
6.	Fertilizer		
	Urea	125.10	0.13
	10:26:26	685.56	0.74
	DAP	697.71	0.75
	SSP	1179.2	1.27
	MOP	287.01	0.31
	10:32:16	1182	1.27
7.	Plant protection	1755.88	1.88
8.	Land revenue	75.56	0.08
9.	Incidental charges	325.45	0.35
10.	Interest on working capital @ 6%	2433.67	2.61
11.	Depreciation on capital assets	9092.69	9.76
12.	Cost-A (Σ 1 to 11)	52163.17	55.98
13.	Rental value of land	20908.18	22.44
14.	Interest on fixed capital @ 11%	16254.41	17.44
15.	Cost-B (Σ 12 to 14)	89325.76	95.86
16.	Family human labour	3853.88	4.14
17.	Cost-C (Σ 15 to 16)	93179.64	100

Table 3: Per hectares profitability in soybean production (₹/ ha)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Physical unit	Physical quantity	Amount (₹)
1.	Return from a main produce	q	18.57	120705.00
2.	Return from by produce	q	2.86	5197.47
3.	Gross return (Σ 1 to 2)	–	–	125902.47
4.	Cost-A	–	–	52163.17
5.	Cost-B	–	–	89325.76
6.	Cost-C	–	–	93179.64
7.	Farm business income (Gross return minus Cost-A)	–	–	73739.3
8.	Family labour income (Gross return minus Cost -B)	–	–	36576.71
9.	Net Profit (Gross return minus Cost-C)	–	–	32722.83
10.	Benefit- Cost ratio (Gross return divided by Cost-C)	–	–	1.35
11.	Per quintal cost of production (Cost-C minus by produce value divided by main produce quantity)	–	–	4737.86

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